

DEVELOPMENT OF HYDROPHOBIC PROTECTION LAYER FOR HIGH-TEMPERATURE IRREVERSIBLE THERMOCHROMICS

Katarina Jenko¹, Nejc Rozman¹, Eva Pogorelc¹, Petra Stražar¹, Matjaž Kunaver¹, Marta Klanjšek Gunde^{1,2}

¹MyCol d.o.o., Ljubljana, Slovenia

²National Institute of Chemistry, Ljubljana, Slovenia

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katarina@mycol.si

Abstract: *MyCol company is developing screen printable irreversible thermochromic ink for temperature indicators. Such indicators indicate heating beyond the prescribed temperature even also in otherwise inaccessible places. The labels can be produced in large quantities and are easy to handle. However, environmental influences, such as UV and visible light, abrasion, exposure to water and other chemicals, can largely reduce or even cancel the coloration. Reduced coloration and possible loss of functionality due to water is the most important factor in many applications. This work presents the effectiveness of various protective coatings applied to the thermochromic indicator layer, focusing on protection from moisture and water.*

Keywords: printed temperature indicators, hydrophobicity, contact angle, functionality, additives.

1 INTRODUCTION

Several industrial processes require a simple proof that a product was heated over the prescribed temperature. Objects in closed spaces where no other technology is applicable to detect the temperature to which such a sample was heated are the most interesting. These applications do not need very tight temperature tolerance. It is more important for the labels to be easily applied and closely attached to the sample surface. The proof of the thermal history should be clearly recognizable by naked eye or by video control. The perfect

solution for such demands is a thermochromic printing ink that permanently changes colour when heated over the prescribed / controlled temperature. Such an ink could be used for indicator labels, when the change of colour is large enough in all conditions that may occur.

MyCol company is currently developing irreversible thermochromic printing ink for various activation temperatures above 60 °C. The prints are opaque white and permanently colour when heated over the activation temperature. However, it is sensitive to moisture and water drops which may considerably influence the functionality of the labels. This drawback drove us to develop a hydrophobic protection layer. It must be fully compatible with the indicator layer which means not only good adhesion on its surface, but also other properties, i.e., it must not inhibit the colouration of the indicator layer. A part of this extensive research and development is described here.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Indicator layer

The irreversible thermochromic ink was synthesized using the original recipe of MyCol company and designed to indicate heating over 70 °C. The active material is entirely organic and 2-hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC) was used as the binder. The ink was screen printed on polypropylene foil (MR BOPP 60 BELA P GL 60, Muflon, Slovenia) and paper (MP CHROM 80 F KR80, Muflon, Slovenia) in 1x1 cm squares and dried at ambient conditions. Here we evaluate the ink that develops black colour, but some other shades are also possible.

Figure 1. Temperature dependent coloration (ΔE) of the indicator.

The temperature-dependent coloration of the indicator layer (Figure 1) shows the total colour difference (ΔE) of the sample before and after heating at temperature T. The samples were kept at the selected temperature for 15

minutes inside a temperature-controlled laboratory oven in 5 °C steps (Kambič, Slovenia); additional point was included at 67 °C. The measurements were made at room temperature using i1 spectrometer (X-Rite). ΔE was calculated in the CIELAB colour space (Schanda, 2007).

2. 2 The influence of water on the functionality of indicator layer

A water drop could appear on the surface of the indicator layer and dry on it. This may happen before heating, when the indicator layer is white, or after heating when it is coloured. The consequences are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The influence of water on the functionality of the indicator. Water was dropped on the indicator before (left) or after activation with heating at 80 °C (right). The results obtained on paper and foil substrates are shown in upper and lower row, respectively

	<i>Water dropped on virgin indicator</i>				<i>Water dropped on activated indicator</i>			
	<i>Virgin</i>	<i>Drop</i>	<i>Dry</i>	<i>Heated</i>	<i>Virgin</i>	<i>Heated</i>	<i>Drop</i>	<i>Dry</i>
<i>Paper</i>								
<i>Foil</i>								

Unactivated indicator layer is white and colours when heated above 70 °C (Figure 1). If the water drop dries on the white indicator, this part of its surface develops a smaller coloration with heating, but this effect does not happen on indicator printed on foil. If the water drop dries on the activated (coloured) indicator, the coloration of the corresponding surface diminishes, more on the paper substrate and less on the foil.

2. 3 Preparation of protective layer

A hydrophobic protective layer was applied to protect the indicator layer from detrimental effects of water and tested for efficiency. Selected commercially available coatings were used as well as a laboratory mixture of the binder and some selected hydrophobic additives. The commercially available substances were two functional-blend hydrophobic waxes Wükoseal® (Münzig Chemie, Germany). The laboratory made protective coating was HEC based binder with 4 different additives using recommended concentrations. This way 6 protective coatings were formulated, giving 7 samples in total (Table 2). The protective coatings were applied over dry indicator layers using 4-sided dumb-bell film

applicator (PA-2040, BYK-Gardner, Germany) with 100 μm clearance. All layers were dried at ambient conditions for 1 day.

Table 2: Protective coatings: base materials and additives.

Sample	Base material	Additive	Additive concentration
1	/	-	-
2	Wükoseal® 805	-	-
3	Wükoseal® 1512	-	-
4	HEC	TP 1500 N	4.5 wt%
5	HEC	TP 1650	6.0 wt%
6	HEC	Wükoseal® 1512	0.75 wt%
7	HEC	Wükoseal® 805	0.75 wt%

2. 4 Coloration measurements

The colour difference (ΔE) was measured between unheated and heated sample (80 °C). The measurements were made for three situations of the same sample – with no influence of water, with water drop dried on unheated sample and the one dried on heated sample. This gives three ΔE values for each sample, showing the influence of water on the functionality of the same indicator in the three possible situations that may occur in a real application.

2. 5 Contact angle measurements

The hydrophobicity of the protective layer was evaluated by pendant drop technique and expressed by contact angle between the water drop and sample surface (Hu & Larson, 2002; Kaplanová et al., 2008). The optical tensiometer One Attension Theta (Biolin Scientific, Sweden) was used for these measurements. The contact angle was evaluated at 1, 5- and 60 s after the 2 μL drop land the sample surface. For each result, the readings obtained with 4 drops were averaged.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The coloration of indicators (Figure 2) depends on the substrate and on the protective layer. On paper, the unprotected sample (1) loses its functionality ($\Delta E < 10$) if water is absorbed either before or after heating (see also Table 1). The protection layer causes lower ΔE in all studied cases, except on sample 2, where the protection from the influence of water is the highest. On foil, the best protection is for sample 3 and similar for sample 7.

Figure 2: Coloration of samples (Table 2) without water (blue), and with water drop dried on unactivated (red) and on the activated states (green). The indicators were printed on paper (left) or on foil (right).

Figure 3: Contact angle of the samples (Table 2) printed on paper (top) and foil (bottom) before (left) and after activation (right), measured at 1, 5 and 60 seconds after drop formation.

The contact angle was measured on activated and unactivated samples in periods 1-, 5- and 60 s after formation of the drop (Figure 3). Within this period of time the drop spreads clearly on samples 6 and 7, but smaller effect was observed elsewhere. The contact angle is the smallest on foil, falling below 80° after 60 seconds on samples 3 and 7, but remains above 80° in all other samples. The largest contact angle is about 130° and remains stable for the analysed period of time for samples 4 and 5 on paper and 4 on foil before activation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A good irreversible thermochromic temperature indicator develops large enough colouration when heated above the controlled temperature which must not be influenced by external factors other than temperature. Here we analysed the influence of water and the protection needed to assure the same coloration regardless of when the droplet was dried on the surface, before or after heating.

In our example, an unacceptable detrimental effect of water on colouration of indicator layer was observed. Therefore, a hydrophobic layer was applied to try to protect the indicator layer from the detrimental effects of water on the functionality of the temperature indicator.

The results show that all the applied coatings are in fact hydrophobic, but this may not necessarily protect the indicator layer against losing the functionality, i.e. diminishing the colour contrast between unheated / unactivated (white) and heated / activated (coloured) states. However, one of the used protective layers appears to be very good for indicators printed on paper.

One of the possible explanations could be that the water droplet protrudes through the hydrophobic layer and causes an effect in the indicator layer. This requires a deeper research on the layer surface and other possible reasons for the cause of the observed phenomenon.

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